

Electrical evaluation of bacterial virulence factors using nanopores

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we propose a novel methodology for the electrical monitoring using nanoporous alumina membranes of virulence factors secreted by bacterial pathogens. Bacterial hyaluronidase (HYAL), which is produced by a number of invasive Gram-positive bacteria, is selected as a model compound to prove the concept. Our electrochemical set-up takes advantage of the flat surface of ITO/PET electrodes for their assembling with the nanoporous membrane. The proposed analytical method, based on the electrical monitoring of the steric/electrostatic nanochannels blocking upon formation of an antibody-HYAL immunocomplex, reached detection limits as low as 64 UI/mL (17.3 U/mg) HYAL. The inert surface of the ITO/PET electrodes together with the anti-biofilm properties of the 20 nm-pore sized alumina membranes allow for culturing the bacteria, capturing the secreted enzymes inside the nanochannels and removing the cells before the electrochemical measurement. Secreted HYAL at levels of 1000 UI/mL (270 U/mg) are estimated in Gram-positive *S. aureus* cultures, while low levels are detected for Gram-

negative *P. aeruginosa* (used as a negative control). Finally, HYAL secretion inhibition by RNAIII-inhibiting peptide (YSPWTNF-NH₂) is also monitored, opening the way to further applications of the developed monitoring system for evaluation of the anti-virulence potential of different compounds. This label-free method is rapid and cheap, avoiding the use of the time consuming sandwich assays. We envisage future applications for monitoring of bacterial virulence/invasion as well as for testing of novel antimicrobial/anti-virulence agents.

KEYWORDS: Nanopores; nanochannels; hyaluronidase; bacteria; virulence factor; electrochemical detection.

INTRODUCTION

Bacterial hyaluronidases (HYAL) are produced by a number of pathogenic Gram-positive bacteria to catalyze the degradation of hyaluronic acid (HA) and initiate infections at the skin or the mucosal surfaces.¹ *Streptococcus*, *staphylococcus*, *streptomyces* or *clostridium* bacteria among others use this enzyme as a virulence factor to destroy the polysaccharide that holds human cells together, making easier for the pathogen to spread through the host tissues.^{2,3} The interest in analytical methods for the detection of this enzyme is related to two main aspects: i) the evaluation of the secreted levels of enzymes for different bacterial species would allow to discriminate between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria and also to classify them in terms of their virulence,⁴ and ii) the evaluation of the enzyme secretion inhibition would allow to propose novel antimicrobial/anti-virulence agents.^{5,6} However, the currently available tools for the detection of this enzyme are quite limited. HYAL is a small protein (Mw = 60 kDa) which makes difficult its detection using traditional immunoassays, e.g. radioimmunoassays (RIA) and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assays (ELISA) that are expensive, time consuming and need hazardous labelling reagents.⁷

In this context, immunosensors appear as an advantageous alternative to the traditional immunoassays, overcoming most of the above mentioned limitations since they are rapid, cheap and allow label-free detection.⁸ Immunosensing technology has also been strongly driven in the last years by the advances in the nanomaterials field, being the outstanding properties of the nanostructured materials approached for the development of improved biosensing systems.⁹ In line with these promising perspective are the recent studies that estimate that the global biosensors market is expected to reach around 21 Billion USD by 2020.¹⁰

In particular, nanopores/nanochannels are among the nanomaterials with higher potential in the biosensing field. Stochastic sensing based on biomolecules translocation through single natural/artificial nanopores has been extensively reported for the detection of proteins, enzymes, DNA strands and even viruses,^{11,12} being the DNA sequencing systems commercially available.¹³ Nanoporous membranes have also been used as sensing platforms for both optical and electrochemical biosensing, taking advantage of interferometric and impedimetric/voltammetric measurements upon biomolecule recognition inside the nanochannels.¹⁴ Nanoporous alumina is one of the main materials used for such purposes, due to its unique structural properties.¹⁵ Sensors for whole bacteria detection on nanoporous alumina based on impedimetric measurements have been reported in the last years.¹⁶⁻¹⁹ However, the detection of secreted biomolecules on live bacterial cultures has not been studied so far.

Under these premises, we propose a novel methodology for the detection of HYAL secretion by Gram-positive bacteria cultures on nanoporous membranes, taking advantage of the anti-biofilm properties of the small pore-sized nanoporous alumina²⁰ and the cell-compatibility of the ITO/PET electrodes²¹ used as transducers. The proposed analytical method is based on the electrical monitoring of nanochannels blocking upon HYAL immunorecognition. The obtained results open the way to future applications for virulent bacteria detection as well as for evaluation of the anti-infective potential of different agents.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Chemicals and equipment

$K_4[Fe(CN)]_6$, (3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane (APTES), [N -(3-dimethylamino) propyl]-N-ethylcarbodiimide (EDC), sulfo N-hydroxysuccinimide (sulfo-NHS) and phosphate buffered saline (PBS) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain). RIP (YSPWTNF-NH₂) was synthesized on demand by Quimigen (Spain). All chemicals were of analytical grade and used as received. All aqueous solutions were prepared in ultrapure water (Milli-Q plus system, Millipore) with 18.2 M Ω cm resistivity. All other chemicals and reagents for bacterial culturing were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich unless otherwise specified. Anodized aluminum oxide filter membranes (Whatman anodisc AAO, 13 mm diameter; 60 μ m thickness; 20 nm pores) and indium tin oxide coated PET (ITO/PET) sheets (surface resistivity 60 Ω /sq) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain).

The electrochemical transducers were ITO/PET pieces of 35x10 mm, defining a working electrode of 8 mm in diameter. Reference and counter electrodes were a silver/silver chloride (CH Instruments, USA) and a platinum wire, respectively. Electrochemical measurements were performed with an Autolab 20 (Eco-chemie, The Netherlands) connected to a PC. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature with a working volume of 500 μ L. High resolution scanning electrical microscope (HRSEM, FEI MAGELLAN 400L XHR, The Netherlands) were used for the optical characterizations. Microplate reader (Infinite M200, Tecan, Austria) was utilized for turbidity measurement to monitor bacterial growth and assess the HYAL activity.

A schematic illustration including all experimental steps is given in the Supporting Information S1.

Bacteria, enzymes and antibodies

Gram-negative *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145) and Gram-positive *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923) bacteria were purchased from American Type Culture Collection (ATCC LGC Standards, Spain). Single *S. aureus* and *E. coli* colonies were prepared on tryptic soy agar (Sigma-Aldrich (Spain) plates using a streaking technique and stored at 4 °C for regular use.

Hyaluronidase from *Streptomyces hyalurolyticus* (EC 4.2.2.1) and anti-hyaluronidase (polyclonal antibody developed in rabbit) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Spain).

Aliquots of this antibody were prepared in 0.01 M PBS buffer, pH 7.4.

Nanoporous alumina membranes functionalization

Nanoporous alumina membranes (20 nm-sized pores) functionalization with specific antibodies was performed following a previously optimized methodology.²² Briefly, membranes were first boiled in milli-Q water for 1 h. After drying in argon, they were immersed in a 5 % acetone solution of APTES for 1 h. The membranes were washed in acetone and baked at 120 °C for 30 min. After that 30 µL of a 10 µg/mL solution of anti-HYAL antibody in PBS buffer containing 5 mM EDC/sulfo-NHS were added for 2 h.

Bacterial culturing in electrochemical cells

The design of the experimental set-up for the *in situ* bacteria culture/electrochemical detection (nanoporous membranes assembled to ITO/PET electrode) is demonstrated in Figure 1. Nanoporous membranes were fixed onto the ITO/PET electrode by physical attachment, which consisted of placing the ITO/PET piece onto a methacrylate block and putting the membrane over the electrode surface. Then, a second block containing a hole of 8 mm in diameter was placed onto the nanoporous membrane, with an O-ring (RS Amidata,

Spain) between them to avoid liquid leakage. The system was fixed with screws, defining an electrochemical cell of approx. 500 μL .

Figure 1. Pictures of the experimental set-up for the bacteria culture and electrochemical detection of secreted HYAL.

For bacterial culturing and *in situ* monitoring of HYAL secretion by electrochemistry, an overnight grown *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* cultures were diluted in TSB until optical density of 0.1 at 600 nm was reached. Then, 500 μ L of each bacteria were placed on the nanoporous membranes and incubated at room temperature for 24 h. Pictures of the bacterial cultures in a set of electrochemical cells are shown at the Supporting Information S2. The cell morphology and growth on membrane surface was assessed by HRSEM analysis. After the time of incubation, the nanoporous membranes were washed twice with PBS and bacterial cells were fixed with 4 % (v/v) formaldehyde at 4 °C overnight. The membranes were washed with PBS and sequentially treated with 25, 50, 75, and 96 % EtOH for 10 min each.

HYAL quantification in standard solutions (PBS) and in bacteria culture medium (TSB) was also performed following a similar procedure, but placing 30 μ L of the HYAL solution instead of the bacteria culture.

Inhibition of HYAL secretion

S. aureus cultures were grown and diluted in TSB as already described. Then, 500 μ L of the bacterial inoculum containing 50 μ g/mL RIP were added into the electrochemical cells and the samples were incubated at room temperature for 24 h. Afterwards, the secretion of HYAL was evaluated by standard turbidity method and our sensing system. For the turbidity measurements, the cells cultures were centrifuged at 4000 g for 20 min. Then, 200 μ L of supernatant were mixed with 200 μ L of 0.8 mg/mL HA (Lifecore Biomedical (USA), Mw = 74 kDa) in 300 mM sodium phosphate buffer, pH 5.35 for 45 minutes at 37 °C. 50 μ L of the reaction mixtures were transferred in 96-well plate and incubated for 10 min with

to 250 μL of 0.1 % bovine serum albumin in 24 mM sodium acetate/79 mM acetic acid, pH 3.75. The absorbance of the samples at 600 nm was measured by microplate reader (Infinite M200, Tecan, Austria). All assays were performed in triplicate and the results expressed as mean value \pm S.D. HYAL (80 UI/mL, Sigma-Aldrich (Spain)) was used as positive control.

Electrochemical evaluation of HYAL produced by bacteria

After washing with PBS buffer, the electrochemical cell containing the nanoporous membrane was filled with 500 μL of a 1 mM $\text{K}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]/0.1$ M KCl. A pre-treatment at -100 mV was applied during 30s and immediately after, a differential pulse voltammetric (DPV) scan from -100 mV to +500 mV (step potential 10 mV, modulation amplitude 50 mV, scan rate 33.5 mV/s) was applied resulting in an analytical signal due to oxidation of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{4-}$ to $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ at approximately +200 mV, whose peak current is chosen as analytical signal. The measurements were carried out at room temperature under non-stirring conditions. Each measurement was performed with a single nanoporous membrane and an ITO electrode, which were discarded after the measurement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Electrochemical detection of HYAL using nanoporous membranes

We propose a novel methodology for HYAL detection on nanoporous alumina membranes based on specific antibodies immobilized in the inner walls of the nanochannels. The antibody-HYAL immunocomplex produces a partial blockage in the diffusion of the electroactive species ($[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$) through the membrane to the electrode, which results in a decrease in the voltammetric signal of oxidation of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$. This

sensing principle was previously reported for other analytes with poor sensitivity,²² which made necessary the use of signal amplification strategies based on sandwich assays with labelled antibodies²³ or the use of nanostructured red-ox indicators.^{24,25} Such poor sensitivity was attributed to the low steric blockage of the electroactive ions diffusion by the immunocomplex. Furthermore, the use of screen-printed carbon electrodes (SPCEs) as transducers in such approaches suffered from important limitations, related to: i) the membrane covering the 3 electrodes (working, reference and counter), what induced unwanted blocking of the reference electrode, leading to unstable signals; ii) the roughness of the working carbon electrode made difficult to keep a constant distance between the nanochannels and the electrode, leading to irreproducibility in the signals, and iii) the low biocompatibility of the carbon and silver materials contained in the SPCE limited its application for studies in cell cultures.

In our novel approach, the experimental set-up allows to improve the system performance, overcoming the above mentioned limitations (Figure 1). We take advantage of the flat surface of the ITO/PET sheets used as a working electrode to improve the membrane/electrode assembling and consequently the system reproducibility. The utilization of small-sized external counter and reference electrodes also assure stable signals. It is worthy to mention that the ITO electrodes are not toxic to both human and bacterial cells,¹⁵ making them ideal for studying live cell cultures.

Moreover, in this particular case, we take advantage of the specific characteristics of the HYAL related to its electrostatic contribution to the nanochannel blockage. The isoelectric point of HYAL (pI 4.9) is below the pH of the red-ox indicator, which means that negatively charged molecules would hinder the access to the electrode of the negatively charged $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, as illustrated in Figure 2a.

Figure 2. a) Scheme (not in scale) of the biosensing system based on nanochannel steric/electrostatic blocking by the antibody-HYAL complex formation. b) (Up) Differential pulse voltammograms (DPVs) obtained for increasing concentrations of HYAL standard solutions (0, 80, 236, 473 and 956 UI/mL, from up to down) in buffer medium. Electrolyte: 1 mM K₄[Fe(CN)₆] / 0.1 M KCl. Scan from -0.1 V to +0.5 V (step potential 10 mV, modulation amplitude 50 mV, scan rate 33.5 mV/s, non-stirred solution); (Down) Effect of HYAL concentration on the voltammetric peak current (analytical signal).

Following such principle, the ability of the system for HYAL detection in standard solutions was evaluated. As shown in Figure 2b, voltammetric signals with sharp peaks at a stable potential were obtained with the optimized set-up. The voltammetric peak current decreased when increasing the HYAL concentration in the range from 80 to 956 UI/mL due to the steric/electrostatic blockage in the nanochannel. The relation of the HYAL

concentration and the peak intensity is adjusted to a linear relationship in this range, with a correlation coefficient of 0.99, according to the following equation:

$$i_p (\mu\text{A}) = -0.0553 [\text{HYAL}] (\text{UI/mL}) + 68 \text{ (Equation 1)}$$

The reproducibility (RSD) of the method is 5 % (n = 3) for HYAL concentration of 236 UI/mL. A limit of detection (LOD, calculated as the analyte concentration giving a signal equal to the blank signal + three times its standard deviation) of 64 UI/mL (17.3 U/mg) of HYAL is estimated. The response time of the system (the time needed to get the signal after the analyte recognition) is 60 seconds. As stated in the Experimental Section, the nanoporous membrane and the ITO electrode were discarded after each measurement, thus avoiding washing/regeneration treatments and fouling problems. The low cost of both materials allows to easily prepare a set of electrochemical cells containing the nanoporous membrane assembled to the ITO/PET electrode for each panel of experiments (as illustrated at the Supporting Information S2).

Similar results were reported for turbidimetric (LOD: 20 U/mg) and capillary zone electrophoresis (LOD: 16.4 U/mg) methods²⁶ developed for determination of hyaluronidase activity in complex samples. These methods, however, include complex methodology, use expensive reagents and are time consuming. The electrochemical method we propose here not only meets all these requirements but also directly detects the enzyme in the sample without the need of its pre-incubation with hyaluronic acid for occurrence of the enzymatic reaction.

In order to evaluate the performance of our sensing system in a real scenario, different amounts of HYAL were spiked in bacterial culture medium (without bacteria) before the electrochemical analysis on the nanoporous membranes. When comparing these results

with the results obtained in buffer, it was observed that slightly more enzyme was needed to observe the same degree of blocking in the channel, with an average recovery of the signal of around 75 % (Supporting Information S3). This means that the performance of the immunoassay is affected in a very low extent by the matrix of the sample, while unspecific adsorption on the nanochannels was not detected. Such low matrix effects are in agreement with what we expected. One of the main properties of the alumina membrane is related to its low protein adsorption. Actually, this is why they are extensively used for filtering: small molecules pass through the nanochannels while big molecules remain out and are easily removed after washing, without adsorption on the membrane. In our specific approach, antibodies are grafted on the amino groups inside the nanochannels using EDC/NHS crosslinking. Without cross-linker, any molecule is adsorbed to the channels. Such low unspecific absorption in complex matrixes such as whole human blood was also previously noticed.²³

Bacterial culturing on nanoporous membranes: evaluation of HYAL secretion

Our interest in the detection of HYAL enzyme is related to two different aspects. First, the evaluation of the secreted levels of HYAL would allow to discriminate between Gram-positive (high secretion) and Gram-negative (low secretion) bacteria and even to classify them in terms of their virulence. Moreover, we could easily assess the anti-virulence/anti-infective potential of novel agents through the decrease in the enzyme secretion/activity.

In this context, both Gram-negative *P. aeruginosa* and Gram-positive *S. aureus* bacteria were cultured on the membranes assembled with the ITO/PET electrode on the optimized electrochemical set-up. 20 nm pore-sized nanoporous alumina membranes are non-toxic materials ideal for culturing bacteria under optimum conditions for the enzyme secretion.

Moreover, they possess bacteria-repelling properties and resist the irreversible bacterial attachment and establishment of biofilms, which if not removed completely before the electrochemical measurements would affect the signal detection due to the unspecific membranes blocking. Previous studies demonstrated that the vertical sidewalls of such cylindrical pores exert electrostatic repulsion and acid–base repulsive forces on the bacterial cells, which are greatly enhanced by the high density of small nanopores.²⁰ ITO/PET electrodes are also ideal transducers for the studies with cell cultures, owing to their biocompatibility that makes them one of the most promising materials for i.e. implantable electrodes.²¹

High resolution scanning electron microscopy (HRSEM) images of the cultured bacteria on the membranes (Figure 3) showed that both bacterial species were able to grow on the membrane surface, without any observable change in the cells morphology.

Figure 3. High resolution scanning electrical microscope (HRSEM) images (top view) of (left) *P. aeruginosa* (Gram-negative) and (right) *S. aureus* (Gram-positive) cells cultured on nanoporous alumina membranes. Inset photo shows the electrochemical cell where the bacteria ($OD_{600} = 0.1$) were cultured.

Furthermore, the cells were individually spread, without any evidence for formation of typical biofilm structures and unspecific membrane blocking. This suggests that bacteria were under optimum conditions for the potential secretion of the HYAL enzyme. During the 24 h culture period, Gram-positive bacteria should be continuously secreting HYAL which will be captured by the antibodies inside the nanochannels, leading to the electrical blocking (Figure 4a). After such period, bacteria are effectively removed before the electrochemical measurement.

Electrochemical results, where voltammograms corresponding to three different cultures of *P. aeruginosa* and of *S. aureus* are further displayed (Figure 4b). The lower peak currents recorded for *S. aureus* indicated a higher extent of nanopores blocking, suggesting a higher secretion of HYAL in comparison with *P. aeruginosa*, as it was expected. This means that the sensing system was able to efficiently discriminate between Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Moreover, the amount of HYAL secreted under such conditions is estimated to be 1000 UI/mL (270 U/mg), according to equation 1. The HYAL production by *S. aureus* was further confirmed through the degradation of HA following a modified agar plate method described before.²⁷ The secretion of HYAL by the Gram-negative *S. aureus* leads to a clear zone formation, which is not observed for *P. aeruginosa* (Supporting Information S4). These results are in agreement with the previously obtained voltammograms.

Figure 4. a) Scheme illustrating the bacteria culture on the nanoporous membranes and the continuous capturing of secreted HYAL by the antibodies inside the nanochannels. b) Voltammograms corresponding to 3 different cultures of *P. aeruginosa* and of *S. aureus*. Bacterial concentration at $\text{OD}_{600} = 0.1$. Incubation time: 24h. DPV parameters as in Figure 2b. c) Analytical signals obtained for *S. aureus* cultures before and after treatment with anti-infective RNAIII-inhibiting peptide (RIP, YSPWTNF-NH₂).

Inhibition of HYAL secretion by quorum-sensing inhibitor: potential tool for evaluation of novel antimicrobial agents

HYAL is one of the main virulence factors of Gram-positive bacteria, so the inhibition of its secretion by anti-infective agents would be required to attenuate the bacterial virulence and potentiate the efficacy of existing antibacterial agents.⁶ In this context, the developed

sensing system emerges as suitable tool for the *in situ* monitoring of bacterial virulence attenuation via the inhibition of HYAL production by bacterial pathogens.

The system was used to evaluate *in situ* the anti-infective potential RNAIII-inhibiting peptide (RIP, YSPWTNF-NH₂). This peptide inhibits bacterial cell-to-cell communication process of *S. aureus* and suppresses the secretion of numerous virulence factors as well as reduces the pathogen adhesion on both mammalian cells and plastic surfaces. RIP has been shown to be an effective inhibitor of *S. aureus* pathogenesis *in vitro* as well *in vivo*, and herein we used it as a model anti-infective compound for the newly developed HYAL sensing system.

The inhibition of HYAL secretion was electrically monitored *in situ* in *S. aureus* cultures. A great inhibition of the analytical signal was observed after the addition of RIP in bacterial surrounding (Figure 4c). Despite its known anti-infective properties,²⁹ the peptide induced inhibition of HYAL secretion by *S. aureus* has never been demonstrated *in vitro* by immunosensing technology. The decreased HYAL activity (production) of RIP treated bacterial culture was further assessed by standard turbidimetric method, being the results in corroboration with the obtained voltammetric signals (Supporting Information S5). All these results reveal the great potential of the designed sensing system for *in situ* monitoring of the specific inhibition of HYAL production upon exposure to anti-virulent actives. Our system could be a useful tool for the evaluation of novel anti-infective agents aimed at reducing the virulence of Gram-positive bacteria. Moreover, the method may be extended for the *in situ* screening of any other protein/enzyme secreted by bacteria, targeting applications in medicine, food analysis and environmental control among others.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we have demonstrated that nanoporous alumina membranes assembled to cells-compatible ITO/PET electrodes can be used to quantify HYAL secretion from Gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*), allowing to discriminate them from Gram-negative ones (*P. aeruginosa*). Bacterial growth and cell surface morphology were not altered onto these membranes, while the unspecific blocking by biofilm is prevented by the anti-fouling properties of the small pore-sized membranes. The electrical method for in situ hyaluronidase secretion monitoring reached detection limits of 64 UI/mL (17.3 U/mg) HYAL. This result is in line with previous reports based on more expensive and time consuming methodologies requiring enzymatic activity assays, such as turbidimetric (LOD: 20 U/mg) and capillary zone electrophoresis (LOD: 16.4 U/mg). Our method is faster and cheaper, allowing to detect the enzyme directly in the sample without the need of its pre-incubation with hyaluronic acid for occurrence of the enzymatic reaction.

The proposed method is of particular interest for the evaluation of the HYAL secretion inhibition by antimicrobial/anti-virulence agents. The proof-of-concept of such application was provided by detecting reduced HYAL secretion upon incubation with known anti-infective peptide, RIP. Such peptide is able to interfere with bacterial cell-to-cell signaling responsible virulence factors production, being in this particular case the inhibition of HYAL production electrically monitored *in situ*. This method holds great potential for the screening of novel antimicrobial agents able to regulate secretion of HYAL and could be extended to other extracellularly produced proteins/enzymes as well.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Comparative of the analytical signals obtained for different concentrations of HYAL in PBS and bacterial culture medium, results for HYAL activity evaluation using plate agar and turbidity methods, schematic illustration of the whole experimental procedure as well as pictures of a set of electrochemical cells where both *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* were cultured.

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Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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ABBREVIATIONS

APTES, (3-Aminopropyl)triethoxysilane; DPV, Differential pulse voltammetric; HRSEM, High resolution scanning electron microscopy; EDC, [N -(3-dimethylamino) propyl]-N-ethylcarbodiimide; HYAL, hyaluronidase; PBS, phosphate buffered saline; RIP, RNAIII-inhibiting peptide; SPCEs, screen-printed carbon electrodes; TSB, tryptic soy broth, sulfo-NHS, sulfo N-hydroxysuccinimide.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Electrical evaluation of bacterial virulence factors using nanopores

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Figure S1. Schematic illustration of the experimental procedure followed for the nanoporous alumina membrane functionalization, antibody immobilization, secreted HYAL capturing and voltammetric detection upon nanochannel blockage.

Figure S2. Representative photographs of a set of electrochemical cells (containing the nanoporous alumina membrane assembled to the ITO/PET electrode) where both *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* were cultured before the SEM analysis or the electrochemical detection of HYAL.

Figure S3. Comparative of the analytical signals obtained for different HYAL concentrations in both PBS (blue bars) and bacteria culture medium (red bars).

Hyaluronidase activity in *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* cultures

HYAL production was assessed by plate agar method as described before. Briefly, 1 % tryptic soy agar was autoclaved at 121 °C for 15 min and then cooled to 45-50 °C. 1 % (w/v) bovine albumin and 0.8 mg/mL hyaluronic acid (Lifecore Biomedical, Mw= 74 kDa) were added under aseptic conditions. Then, 20 mL of the agar were poured into sterile plastic plates and allowed to solidify. Three wells of 9 mm in diameter were aseptically punched into the agar and 100 μL of culturing medium were pipetted into each well. After overnight incubation at 37 °C, the plates were flooded with 2 N acetic acid and the zones of clearing (HYAL activity) were visualized. Purified hyaluronidase (Sigma, H-3506) was used as positive control in all the experiments.

Figure S4. HYAL activity of *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*. Zones of clearing are visualized against a background of opaque precipitated hyaluronic acid conjugated to bovine serum albumin. Purified HYAL (Sigma, H-3506) was used as a positive control.

Figure S5. HYAL activity in presence and absence of RIP was evaluated using standard turbidity method. Lower activity, probably due to the reduced production of HYAL, was observed in presence of the inhibitory peptide.